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IDENTIFICATION AND REDUCTION OF SOME OF AVOIDABLE EXERGY LOSSES IN A LARGE INDUSTRIAL STEAM HEAT AND POWER PLANT

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Introduction

In the time of the rising energetic media prices and lowering net incomes, the industrial companies grow more concerned about the efficiency of the energetic media production, distribution and consumption. Through the optimization of the steam and electricity production processes in a central industrial steam heat and electricity plant, an increase of the qualitative production parameters by several percents can be achieved. The top on the priority list represent those measures that can be realized without large investment needs and include both a simple technical solution and a short pay back period. In order to reveal such potential measures and to persuade the competent technicians and managers about its attractiveness, an external “help” is often needed. This means skilled people from outside of the given industry who, besides their professional skills often contribute with a new point of view, since in many cases the industrial companies fail in supporting their internal capacities in search of new ideas and solutions.

There are a number of useful and successful approaches to the optimization of the combined heat and power units, starting with the well proven empirical attitude, through the comparative analyses of various unit consumptions and productions, supported by the marginal analysis [1,2] and graphic – numerical tools for the cogeneration potential exploitation [3-5] and lastly the thermodynamic modeling of the whole system [6-10], being the most complex and tedious approach. Fortunately, the above mentioned ways can be successfully combined, yielding quite simple and reliable computation and optimization procedures. This paper intends to demonstrate, how the empirical rules used in the energy audits can intertwine with the more scientific thermodynamic (e.g. exergetic) analysis giving good results even in complex systems case studies. At the same time the authors thereby hope to contribute to the knowledge transfer between the scientific community and the industry, thus striving to fulfill one of the aims of the corresponding author’s doctoral study. The authors chose one of the largest industrial steam heat and power plants in Slovakia as a suitable subject for the optimization purposes.

The paper is divided into following sections: a short description of the system under study; a short review of the basic exergetic analysis principles; formulation of the appropriate rules guiding to the localization of the avoidable exergy losses; the achieved results and finally some concluding remarks.

The industrial steam heat and power plant description

The considered industrial steam heat and power plant, schematically visualized in the **Figure 1**, consists of five steam boilers, two extractive – condensing steam turbines, two backpressure steam turbines, boiler feed water regenerative heating chain and ancillary devices.

Figure 1. The scheme of the most important material stream in the considered central steam heat and power plant.

The condensate from the extraction-condensing steam turbines is step by step heated in the blow down cooler, then in the condenser of the leakage steam and afterwards is heated in three low pressure feed water heaters by the low pressure bleeds from the steam turbines. The final condensate temperature is 135 °C and then it is pumped to the deaerator.

The rest of the boiler feed water is prepared in the low pressure regenerative heaters of the backpressure steam turbines. The steam used in the first heater preheats the chemically treated water from 40 °C to 105 °C by the 0.17 MPa backpressure steam and in the second heater, water is heated to 125 °C by a regenerative turbine bleed and is pumped to the deaerators.

Besides the heated water, the deaerators receive the high pressure condensates from the high pressure feed water heaters, from the steam preheaters of the boiler combustion air and from the liquid fuel preheater. The resulting water is heated in the deaerators to 155 °C by direct contact with the 0.55 MPa steam. The heated and deaerated water is then pumped with the high pressure pumps through two high pressure feed water heaters and is stepwise heated up to 200 to 230 °C (depending on the actual pressure of the regenerative turbine bleeds). Finally, the water enters the steam boilers, where a high pressure superheated steam is raised (9.4 MPa, 530 °C).

The produced steam enters the steam turbines at approximately 8.5 MPa and 525 °C. Three steam mains leave the central steam heat and power plant: the 3.6 MPa one, the 1.1 MPa one and the 0.55 MPa one. Besides this steam pressure levels, a 4 to 5 MPa steam can be extracted from two steam turbines if there is lack of the 3.6 MPa steam production capacity. The rest of the expanding steam is either extracted in the regenerative bleeds, or condenses in the low pressure part of the condensing turbines, or expands to 0.17 MPa backpressure and is used internally for feed water preheating.

Stream number	Stream description	P (MPa)	t (°C)	h (kJ/kg)
1	Liquid fuel	2	170	350
2	Combustion air	0.1	15	15
3	Preheated combustion air ^{\$}	0.1	80 to 130	80 to 130
4	Flue gas	0.1	180	210
5	High pressure live steam	9.4	530	3457
6	Boiler blow down	10.1	311	1409
7	Flash steam from blow down flash	0.55	155	2753
8	Blow down	0.55	155	656
9	Cooled down blow down	0.5	45	189
10	High pressure steam extraction	3.6	360 [*]	3126 [*]
11	Steam for boiler surfaces cleaning and fuel dispersion	3.6	360 [*]	3126 [*]
12	High pressure steam bleed	2.3	375	3187
13	High pressure steam bleed	1.35	340	3129
14	Steam extraction	1.1	300	3048
15	Steam extraction	0.55	220	2895
16	Steam to the deaerator	0.55	220	2895
17	Steam to the combustion air preheater	0.55; 1.1	See the streams 14,15	
18	Steam delivery to the customers	0.55; 1.1; 3.6	See the streams 10, 14, 15	
19	Intermediate pressure steam bleed	0.37	185	2830
20	Low pressure steam bleed (condensing steam turbines) or backpressure steam from one of the backpressure ones	0.17	140	2751
21	Low pressure steam bleed ⁺	0.05	81	2622
22	Low pressure steam to the steam condensers ⁺	0.008	41	2480
23	Steam condenser inlet cooling water	0.15	20	84
24	Steam condenser outlet cooling water	0.1	30	126
25	Fresh make-up demineralised water	0.2	25	105
26	Mixture of the steam condensates and the make-up water	1	35	147
27	Water flow into the low temperature preheating	0.9	60	252
28	Water flow into the deaerator	0.7	135	568
29	Steam condensate from the combustion air preheater	0.55	155	656
30	Steam condensate from the high pressure feed water heater #1	1.35	193	823
31	Steam condensate from the high pressure feed water heater #2	2.3	220	942
32	Deaerated water	12.5	153	653
33	Boiler feed water	12	220	946
34	Steam turbine leakage steam	0.07	110	2700

Table 1. Typical parameters of the most important material streams in the central steam heat and power plant. ^{\$} - the temperature of the preheated air varies from boiler to boiler; ^{*} - conditions at the exit of the steam desuperheater; ⁺ - wet steam.

The boiler blow down rate is approximately 3.5 % of the produced steam rate, which ranges from 400 tons pre hour in summer to 750 tons per hour in winter. The blow down is a boiling liquid at 10 MPa and it is flashed in a single step to 0.55 MPa. The flash steam is led to the deaerators and the boiling 0.55 MPa condensate enters the blow down cooler and is finally discarded at 45 °C.

The boiler combustion air is preheated in the steam heaters before entering the flue gas/air recuperators in the boilers, in order to keep the flue gas stack temperature sufficiently high (170 to 190 °C as a prevention from the SO_x condensation). The steam heaters in the four smaller boilers use the 0.55 MPa steam and that in the fifth boiler can use either the 0.55 MPa steam or the 1.1 MPa steam. Currently, the 1.1 MPa steam is used in this heater.

Approximately 15 tons per hour of the 3.6 MPa steam are used internally in the boiler station; the bigger part of it being throttled down to a lower pressure (from 1 to 1.7 MPa) and injected into the steam boilers as a heat exchange surfaces cleaning medium. The remaining 3.6 MPa steam consumption is found in liquid fuel preheating and in direct steam use for liquid fuel dispersion in the boilers.

The steam turbine condensers are cooled by approximately 3000 m³/h cooling water each; the cooling water flow is kept constant at the highest possible value throughout the whole year. In the smaller condenser the water warms up by 10 °C and in the larger one by 15 °C.

The exergy – basic definitions and the field of application

The exergy is defined as that portion of the energy itself or of the energy of a material stream that can theoretically (by the Carnot cycle) be transformed into the useful work. If we define the reference state by its specific enthalpy h_o , specific entropy s_o and thermodynamic temperature T_o , we can calculate the specific exergy b of a physical stream, characterized by its specific enthalpy h and specific entropy s as (1):

$$b = h - h_o - T_o \cdot (s - s_o) \quad (1)$$

Similarly, if an amount of heat Q is available at a temperature T , its exergy is obtained simply by multiplying Q with the Carnot factor (2):

$$B = Q \cdot \left(1 - \frac{T_o}{T} \right) \quad (2)$$

For a process unit with i inlet streams and j outlet streams following equation holds true:

$$\sum_i^* B_i \geq \sum_j^* B_j ; \sum_i^* B_i = \sum_j^* B_j + I \quad (3)$$

This means that the exergy is not a conservative quantity; the equality sign is valid only for a reversible (and thus theoretical) process. The real processes like the combustion, the heat transfer, the expansion and compression, the pressure losses and many others are inherently irreversible.

I denotes the exergy lost in the given process and is thus the object of minimization in the exergy analysis.

In a real process analysis, one has to distinguish between the avoidable and inherent exergy losses. As an example, the combustion process in the boiler is inherently irreversible and is thus accompanied by significant exergy losses. The biggest portion of them is inherent and just a very small portion of them can be recovered for example by decreasing the excess of the combustion air or by better boiler insulation. Those hypothetical measures would result in increased boiler efficiency and consequently in higher steam production but since the excess air decrease would probably require better (more costly) regulation or/and a new burner and the better boiler insulation

is costly as well, those measures are economically not feasible. As a general conclusion we must further deal just with those exergy losses that can be recovered in an economically feasible way and may therefore be termed “avoidable”.

In a real system, where a lot of data are either not measured or the measurement accuracy can be doubted, it makes less sense to develop a complex model of that system. In some cases one has to rely on the information provided by the system operators. Without a loss of accuracy, the complex model can be transformed into a kind of perturbation analysis, where the properties of the system are calculated at a chosen basic state and, provided that the deviation from the basic state is small, the new system properties can be obtained from the basic system ones by using its marginal parameters. [1,2,11] This fits very well to our optimization purposes, since the below proposed system changes (“deviations” from the basic state) can be considered sufficiently small.

The considerations about the computational procedure

Since most of the proposed system modifications affect the backpressure electricity production, we have to consider, that from the energetic point of view, it is a very effective process and in most cases, the heat consumption in the steam for the production of backpressure electricity does not exceed 4 to 4.2 GJ/MWh and that the marginal heat consumption can be even a little lower. The explanation for the difference between the theoretical value of 3.6 GJ/MW and the observed values lies in the energy losses in the shaft work to electricity transformation process as well as in the fact that the leakage steam from the steam turbine must be condensed (and the steam condensing heat is thus usually lost). This value can also incorporate the internal electricity consumption due to the operation of the ancillary devices (pumps, fans, etc).

Considering the work of Varbanov and his colleagues, [7], the marginal live steam consumption values represent the slope of the steam turbine consumption characteristics. As is stated in that paper, they are related to the difference of the specific stem enthalpies before and after an adiabatic expansion from the state of the live steam to the corresponding pressure; multiplied and divided by several factors representing the turbine operating parameters and its output. Since the resulting value of these factors often is close to unity, one can (as a good approximation) consider the marginal live steam consumption to be the reciprocal of the corresponding steam adiabatic expansion enthalpy difference. Theoretically, the marginal steam expansion process is thus a process of zero-exergy losses, because of the equality of the specific entropies of the live steam and the steam after an adiabatic expansion. Even if considering the accompanying exergy losses due to the mixing of the steam after the expansion, the fuel combustion and the steam generation process; the corresponding unit exergy losses can be expected to be much lower than the overall ones.

p_o (MPa) / t_o (°C)	8.5 / 525				
p_k (MPa)	3.6	1.1	0.55	0.17	condensation
Marginal live steam consumption (t/MWh)	22	9.5	6.4	4.9	3.2
Steam state after an adiabatic expansion	380 °C	230 °C	saturated steam	wet steam, 92 % dryness	-

Table 2. Marginal live steam consumption values for the steam expanding from the live steam conditions to the various pressure levels and the corresponding steam state after an adiabatic expansion.

The **table 2** gives an overview of the marginal steam consumptions for the backpressure electricity production and the hypothetical steam conditions after an adiabatic expansion. This information will be very useful in the calculation process, since it represents the properties of the basic system which undergoes several small perturbations. The marginal steam consumptions are deemed not to be affected by the perturbations.

The avoidable exergy losses localization

As is obvious from the definition of the exergy and the exergy losses; the processes with the most extensive exergy losses in a common central steam heat and power plant usually are: the combustion processes and the steam production, the steam expansion in the steam turbines, the heat transfer and the steam throttling.

The “golden rules” applicable in the avoidable exergy losses localization are, according to our experience the following:

1. Look for the processes where cold streams are heated by hot streams and the heat transfer driving force is too high. Try to find other hot streams suitable for the heat transfer operation with resulting lower heat transfer driving force.
2. Look for the processes with a large pressure drop, especially for the steam throttling before use. Try to use a steam ejector rather than a reduction valve if the process allows it. Try to remove those unnecessary pipe fittings that cause an extensive pressure drop.
3. Look for heat transfer processes which could be performed in more steps rather than in a single one (heat consumption: water heating; heat release: condensates and blow down flashing). Try to usefully integrate the waste heat.
4. Examine carefully the part-load processes. The way they should be performed is not necessarily the same than at full load.
5. Examine the non – typical processes and devices and the way they are operated. You may learn something new and/or it is more probable to find some operational reserves in such devices.

These rules fit very well into the works of Kalitventzeff et al [3-5], where the application of such rules is considered as the exploitation of the available cogeneration potential, which of course, is our aim as well.

As for the combustion itself, little can be done in order to decrease the irreversibility of the process in a standard steam boiler in an economically sound way. The steam parameters are limited; the excess of the combustion air is controlled. The blow down rate is given by the available water quality and by the chemical water treatment. We see some limited operational area in the combustion air steam preheating and in the internal steam consumption for the boiler heat transfer surfaces cleaning.

If evaluating the steam expansion in the steam turbines, we have to realize that the pressure levels of the steam mains are more or less fixed (given by the needs of the external consumers which are not subject to an analysis at the moment) and that of the regenerative steam bleeds depend on the steam mass flow through the turbines. The steam condensing pressure is given by the available cooling water mass flow and its temperature. The only steam exiting flow, whose parameters may be changed, is the backpressure (0.17 MPa) from one of the backpressure steam turbines. It may seem beneficial to decrease its pressure, but this option must be examined very carefully. At decreased steam pressure, the exiting steam might become nearly saturated and there is a risk of condensate

droplets formation which must not be allowed. The overall electricity production increase is questionable as well: on the one hand the unit electricity production by the steam expansion to the backpressure increases; but on the other one its mass flow decreases because of its lesser ability (lower condensing temperature) to heat the cold water. Moreover, the water must be heated in the deaerators to 153 °C and the colder is the water at their inlet, the higher is the 0.55 MPa steam consumption. Thus a part of the steam, previously expanding to 0.17 MPa now expands just to 0.55 MPa and less electricity is produced as a result. As a result we see no space for the decrease of the steam mains pressure at the moment.

The heat transfer processes include the boiler feed water heating, the air preheating by steam and the usage of the boiler blow down and the high pressure condensates from the feed water heaters. Since there are three parallel blow down expanders in the boiler room, we tentatively suggest a two stage blow down expansion instead the present single stage one and the third blow down expander may instead be used for the expansion of the high pressure condensates to 1.1 MPa before entering the deaerators. Thereby, a part of the condensate and blow down heat content could be transformed to a steam with higher pressure than 0.55 MPa and henceforth more electricity could be produced. We also see a possibility for the reduction of the exergy losses in the steam air preheating section and subsequent electricity production increase. As mentioned above, one of the steam air heaters can be operated on 1.1 MPa as well as on 0.55 MPa steam; presently the 1.1 MPa steam is used. By switching to the 0.55 MPa steam, the steam consumption in the given heater lowers somewhat but on the other hand, the unit electricity production increases. There may be a little decrease of the boiler steam output, because of the somewhat colder combustion air; thus the whole boiler and steam turbine balance needs to be recalculated.

Lastly, as mentioned before, a part of the steam consumed internally in the boiler room, is throttled from 3.6 MPa to 1.7 MPa and less; we will examine the possibility to replace the throttling by a steam ejector, whereby a portion of the 1.1 MPa steam could be utilized, resulting in increased electricity production.

As a logical continuation of the above mentioned decrease of the steam pressure for the air steam preheating, we analyzed the possibility of switching from 0.55 MPa steam to the 0.17 MPa steam in the air preheaters of those three boilers, where the maximum required preheated air temperature does not exceed 110 °C. This would mean an additional electricity production surplus. Nevertheless, the following issues need to be elucidated if the cogeneration potential has to be fully exploited:

1. Is there a sufficient 0.17 MPa steam production reserve?
2. How do the heat transfer conditions change and what is the maximum achievable air temperature when the existing air steam heaters are operated on the 0.17 MPa steam?
3. Is there enough space to place an additional air steam heaters if the existing ones, operated on the 0.17 MPa steam can not preheat the air sufficiently? What is the associated cost of such measure and is the related pay back period acceptable?

The results of the preliminary analysis, based on the data acquired from the given industry indicate that:

- The 0.17 MPa steam production reserve is sufficient except for the coldest winter days.
- The highest preheated air temperatures are needed when the boiler outputs decrease, which is caused by the changed heat transfer conditions in the boilers.
- At the same time the overall heat transfer coefficient in the steam air heaters is lower because of the decreased air volumetric flow. Such conditions appear mainly in summer, thus it is apparent that both the decreased heat transfer driving force (the logarithmic

mean temperature difference) as well as the lower overall heat transfer coefficient counterpart the lower heat flux needed to preheat the air.

- The existing air steam heaters will thus not be able to preheat the air sufficiently, especially in summer and generally at lower boiler steam outputs. The maximum achievable preheated air temperatures range from 65 °C in winter to 80 °C in summer which is 15 to 25 °C less than needed. Additional air steam heaters are thereby needed for all three boilers, they should most likely be operated on the 0.55 MPa steam.

A detailed techno – economic analysis is to be carried out; it will show if the exergy losses to be recovered by this proposal can be considered avoidable in an economic feasible way.

Analyzing the feed water preparation system we recently discovered that a part (approximately 15 %) of the deaerated water by-passes the high pressure feed water heaters which subsequently decreases the backpressure electricity production. According to our preliminary calculations the loss of the electricity production lies between 500 and 1000 kW. In our further work we will try to recover at least a part of this loss by proposing and examining the full exploitation of the feed water heaters capacities.

The computation of the exergetic losses decrease for the case of the blow down expansion

The reference state chosen for the computation of the stream exergies is: 25 °C, boiling water. In order to calculate the exergy losses correctly, we needed to estimate the exergy content of the fuel used. It is a liquid fuel with the following mass fractions (%): C – 87.70, S – 0.93, Water – 0.05, H – 11.32. The exergy of a fuel can be calculated by multiplying its lower heating value with a correction factor Φ . The correlation for its calculation was found in [6] (4):

$$\phi = 1,0374 + 0,0159.H / C + 0,0567.O / C \quad (4)$$

The symbols H/C and O/C represent the respective atomic ratios in the fuel. The obtained Φ factor's value is 1.062.

The average yearly blow down rate in the analyzed central heat and power plant is 19.5 tons per hour (t/h). In the following **table 3** we show the results of the material and the enthalpic balance computations.

Case	Single stage expansion to 0.55 MPa	Double stage expansion to 1.1 and 0.55 MPa
Exergy in the blow down, GJ/h	8.05	8.05
First stage flash steam mass flow, t/h	7.0	6.1
First stage boiling liquid mass flow, t/h	12.5	13.4
Second stage flash steam mass flow, t/h	-	0.8
Second stage boiling liquid mass flow, t/h	-	12.6
Exergy in the flash steam total, GJ/h	5.15	5.70
Recovered exergy, GJ/h	-	0.55 (154 kW)

Table 3. The results of the blow down expansion computations.

As can be seen in the case of the double stage expansion, most of the steam was produced at 1.1 MPa. This steam replaces a portion of the 1.1 MPa steam extracted from the steam turbines which further expands to 0.55 MPa to balance its deficit. However, the energetic content of the 1.1 MPa flash steam is somewhat lower than that of the 1.1 MPa 230 °C steam (see the **table 2**). In order

to cover the heat (and mass) deficits at both the 1.1 MPa and 0.55 MPa pressure level, an increase in the steam production by 400 kg/h is needed. The marginal heat efficiency of the steam boiler was set to 90 %. The additional heat input in the fuel was calculated with respect to the 20 °C water (the steam condensates from the external steam consumers are not returned to the central heat and power plant) and the further contribution of the low pressure and high pressure feed water heaters to both steam and electricity production was neglected as well as the changes in the state or the mass flow of any of the remaining material streams in the **figure 1**. The **table 4** sums up the computation results.

Increase in the heat input in the fuel, kW	Increase in the exergy input in the fuel, kW	Increase in the live steam exergy, kW	Decrease of the exergy of the resulting 1.1 and 0.55 MPa steam [§] , kW	Exergy consumption increase in the steam turbine ⁺ , kW	Increase in the produced electricity, kW	Specific fuel heat input consumption, GJ/MWh
430	454	214	143	500	360	4.30

Table 4. The summary of the double stage blow down expansion computations. [§] - due to the change of the steam temperatures as a result of the changed steam mass flows; ⁺ - includes the recovered exergy by the double stage blow down expansion and the decrease of the exergy in the resulting 1.1 and 0.55 MPa steam.

In order to compare between several possibilities of the exergy losses decrease, we can introduce the marginal exergetic efficiency, defined by (5):

$$\eta_{ex,marg} = \frac{\Delta P_{el}}{\sum_i \Delta B_i^* - \sum_j \Delta B_j^*} \quad (5)$$

In (5), the change in the electric output is divided by the difference between the sums of the exergy fluxes changes in the inlet streams *i* and in the outlet streams *j* except the electric output. In this particular case, the $\sum_i \Delta B_i^*$ is calculated as (454+154) kW and the $\sum_j \Delta B_j^*$ is equal to -143 kW.

Finally, for the marginal exergetic efficiency we obtain the value 48 %, which is far more than that of the overall exergetic efficiency. The specific fuel heat input consumption 4.3 GJ/MWh is more or less what could be expected when multiplying the backpressure electricity production efficiency with a common thermal efficiency of a steam boiler.

The two stage blow down expansion can be, of course, performed in a different manner. We see a possibility for a further increase of the electricity production in the increase of the first expansion pressure level. Possible expansion steam consumers are the high pressure feed water heaters operated on the 1 to 1.5 MPa and on the 1.8 to 2.9 MPa steam. Theoretically the optimum pressure level is given by the optimum difference of the saturation temperatures between the blow down and the first and second expansion step steam. The blow down temperature is 310 °C and the second expansion step is set to 0.55 MPa (155 °C); the optimal saturation temperature is the average of these temperatures, e.g. 233 °C. This gives a steam pressure of approximately 3 MPa. Thus the best solution suggests expanding the steam either to the 3.6 MPa steam main or to the pressure needed in the feed water heaters. In our further work we will examine these alternatives more deeply.

The same computational procedure can be applied in order to evaluate the contribution of the expansion of the high pressure condensates to 1.1 MPa prior to entering the deaerators and that of the switching of the air preheater heating steam pressure from 1.1 to 0.55 MPa.

The summary of the localized exergy losses and the achievable increase in the backpressure electricity production yields a potential of more than 1 MW. We will try to deliver a more detailed report about the recent situation in one of the relevant scientific papers.

Conclusions

The aim of this preliminary study was to assess the potential of the presented combined empiric – thermodynamic approach for the localization and reduction of some of the exergy losses in a complex industrial combined heat and power plant. Without a substantial loss of precision we were able to quantify the backpressure electricity production increase possibilities in a system with several quantities (especially flow rates) not measured correctly. The final, more detailed analysis will be provided to the given industry managers and technicians in order to contribute to the knowledge transfer between the scientific community and the industry.

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